

KEY INDICATORS

With 644,520 hectares (2022), Romania had the largest organic farmland area in the EU-13 countries and ranked ninth in the EU in 2022. In terms of organic area share, it was below the EU average (10.6%). However, growth was substantial, with farmland growing almost 30-fold in 2001-2022. Retail sales data is not available for Romania.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

28,700 ha (0.2%)

644,520 ha (4.7%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

2,145.7%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

14,400 ha (0.2%)

338,942 ha (3.8%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

21,233 ha (6.7%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

14,000 ha (0.3%)

214,657 ha (5.0%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

352 MT (3.0%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

N/D

12,598 (0.4%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

6

Processors

N/D

203

Importers

N/D

25

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

4,415 MT

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN ROMANIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat and Ministry of Agriculture Romania, 2000-2023

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Romania CAP strategic plan provides for a 167% increase in supported organic area by 2027 compared with 2018, albeit from a low base. The payment rates are unchanged compared with the previous period, and overall expenditure is forecast to increase by 73%, resulting in a decrease in expenditure per ha of 35%. This implies that the proportion of higher value crops is projected to be reduced. Conversion payments are higher than maintenance, in particular for arable and fruit crops

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	183 kha	488 kha (+167%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	1.4%	3.5% (+150%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	56%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	42 M€	73 M€ (+73%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	232 €	150 € (-35%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	389 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	2,447 M€	9.4%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,706 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	15,611 M€	2.5%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	143	293	500	620	530
	2023	P2	143	293	500	620	530
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	129	218	431	442	479
	2023	P2	129	218	431	442	479
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+11%	+34%	+16%	+40%	+11%
	2023		+11%	+34%	+16%	+40%	+11%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The organic action plan for 2023-2030 is Romania's first. It has a strong focus on market development and information initiatives, building on RDP resources. The 2030 target reflect the low starting position.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	2023-30	6% of UAA by 2030	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

PRODUCTION

Support for smaller farms and environmentally certified social/care farms

MARKETS

Investment aid for marketing and processing; expansion, diversification of under-represented sectors; producer organisations; public procurement for environmental benefits; pilot projects for organic catering, tourism; export development; trade fair participation; protection of organic labels and terms; improved control systems; import testing

INFORMATION

Consumer information, promotion, events, debates, festivals, national organic day; expansion of advisory centres; network of demonstration farms; knowledge exchange supported by RDP AKIS measures; modules and programmes in colleges and universities; support for workplaces on organic farms; professional training courses; regional training centres; research on technical and sustainability issues; EIP operational groups; Horizon Europe participation; market studies with statistical databases, websites and search engines; annual consumer survey

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Romania is about 7%. Aquaculture is not mentioned in the organic action plan. Romania was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding, if any, is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.